

AN AUTONOMOUS FUTURE?

A survey of autonomous shipping with special emphasis on the challenges posed by international law and the necessity of new international regulation.

Frederik Rogiers

Ghent University – Maritime Institute

Supervisor:

Prof. Dr. Frank Maes

Assessors:

Prof. Dr. An Cliquet

Dr. Martin Unfried

Scientific Paper written in fulfillment of the requirements of the Gandaius Academy Port Management.

2021 – 2022

Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. A QUESTION OF TERMINOLOGY	5
3. DEGREES OF AUTONOMY	6
4. BENEFITS OF AUTOMATION?	8
4.1 ECONOMIC BENEFITS	9
4.2 A REDUCED NEED FOR SEAFARERS	10
4.3 NO MORE HUMAN-INDUCED ACCIDENTS	11
4.4 ORGANIZATIONAL BENEFITS	12
4.5 DESIGN BENEFITS	13
5. THE EVOLUTION TOWARDS UNMANNED AND AUTONOMOUS SHIPPING	13
5.1 FROM HUMBLE MILITARY BEGINNINGS ...	13
5.2 TO GREATLY VARIED USES ...	16
6. CAN A MASS BE CONSIDERED A SHIP OR VESSEL?	18
6.1 SHIP OR VESSEL?	18
6.2 THE SILENCE OF THE LOSC	19
6.2.1 THE TEXT OF THE CONVENTION	19
6.2.2 AN EVOLUTIONARY INTERPRETATION?	21
6.3 OVERWHELMED BY THE IMO	22
6.4 WHAT OF OTHER SOURCES?	25
7. CONCLUSION: THE NECESSITY OF NEW INTERNATIONAL REGULATION?	27
BIBLIOGRAPHY	28

1. Introduction

“The era of autonomy on the world’s oceans has indeed arrived.”¹

1. While the occasional altercation between great powers is nothing new of itself, December 15th, 2016 did see a new kind of diplomatic incident. On this day, the Chinese Navy seized an unmanned US underwater vehicle in the South China Sea close to the Philippines.² The Chinese believed the unmanned vehicle to be illegally present within its claimed waters,³ while the US believed it was merely exercising its freedom of navigation,⁴ with the glider also being entitled to sovereign immunity as a government vessel.⁵ While the glider was returned to US forces after five days of intense negotiation,⁶ the stage was set for a contentious legal debate that is unsettled to this day.

Fig. 1: A U.S. Navy buoyancy glider similar to the one seized by Chinese forces.⁷

2. While this form of “lawfare” in itself is nothing surprising – Grotius’ famous *Mare Liberum* was after all in the first place a sophisticated piece of advocacy on behalf of the Dutch East India Company⁸ – the legal challenges presented by Automation are as new as they can be.⁹ The latter concept is however a near universal evolution, which has over the past decades disrupted sector after sector, before arriving in the world of international shipping.¹⁰

¹ Joel Coito, ‘Maritime autonomous Surface Ships: New Possibilities – And Challenges – In Ocean Law and Policy’, *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2021, vol. 97, 306.

² Missy Ryan & Dan Lamothe, ‘Pentagon: Chinese Naval Ship Seized an Unmanned U.S. Underwater Vehicle in South China Sea’, *Washington Post*, 17 December 2016, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/checkpoint/wp/2016/12/16/defense-official-chinese-naval-ship-seized-an-unmanned-u-s-ocean-glider/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

³ X, ‘Nine-dash line’, *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nine-dash_line, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

⁴ Art. 58 LOSC iuncto art. 87 (1) (a) LOSC.

⁵ Art. 95 iuncto art. 96 LOSC.

⁶ Jane Perlez & Matthew Rosenberg, ‘China Agrees to Return Seized Drone, Ending Standoff, Pentagon Says’, *The New York Times*, 17 December 2016, <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/12/17/world/asia/china-us-drone.html>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁷ Sam LaGrone, ‘Updated: Chinese Seize U.S. Navy Unmanned Vehicle’, *USNI News*, 16 December 2016, <https://news.usni.org/2016/12/16/breaking-chinese-seize-u-s-navy-unmanned-vehicle>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁸ Richard Barnes, David Freestone and David M. Ong, ‘The Law of the Sea: Progress and Prospects’ in David Freestone, Richard Barnes, and David Ong (eds.) *The Law of the Sea, Progress and Prospects*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2006, 12.

⁹ It should however be stated that as will be clarified under part. 5, unmanned ships have been in use for as early as the Classical Period.

¹⁰ Paul W. Pritchett, ‘Ghost Ships: Why the Law Should Embrace Unmanned Vessel Technology’, *Tulane Maritime Law Journal*, 2015, vol. 40, no. 1, 198.

3. Today, autonomous technology is developing faster than most people can afford to follow, blazing into a new era of navigation.¹¹ With this speed of development come both optimism and fear, comparable as they are to the writings of Jules Verne and his tin men¹² or Isaac Asimov and his dominating artificial intelligence.¹³ The 2017 cyberattacks against MAERSK at least show that fear for evolutions in cyberspace is not unfounded,¹⁴ even if the operational and economic benefits of remote-controlled and autonomous shipping seem legion at first glance.¹⁵

4. What is equally as numerous however, are the legal challenges presented by the introduction of automation in shipping. The terms “ship” and “vessel” were never determined in the 1982 Law of the Sea Convention¹⁶ and have as many definitions as there are treaties that utilize the concepts themselves. Maritime Law on the other hand has for its long history been underpinned by the assumption that all ships or vessels would be under the command of a master and managed by a crew.¹⁷ Ever increasing autonomy is challenging this assumption, with up to a 1000 autonomous surface ships already operating worldwide.¹⁸ While the International Maritime Organization¹⁹ has already begun to research how to deal with these changes,²⁰ the debate is far from over, with uncertainty being today’s keyword.

5. The amount of ink that has been spilled on the legal challenges presented by autonomous shipping is already substantial. However, a great deal of articles either present too broad a view, thus failing to go deep enough into the substance matter of the challenges or only look at a few treaties. The present paper aims to present a state of affairs as it stands today, taking into account past writings, a broad view of international treaties and a narrow focus to the question of whether a MASS can be considered a ship or a vessel under the LOSC and the different instruments ordering the maritime domain. Before discussing these items however, the author shall first clarify the terminology used throughout the paper, as well as go into more detail on the meaning of “autonomy”. Hereafter the evolutions in autonomous shipping up to this point in time shall be concretized before going into some more detail on the many benefits autonomous shipping presents.

¹¹ Kai Tong & Tong Xiao, ‘International Symposium on the Law of the Sea – Development Challenges and Prospects’, *China Oceans Law Review*, 2021, vol. 17, no. 3, 161.

¹² Arthur B. Evans, ‘Jules Verne’s Dream Machines: Technology and Transcendence’, *Extrapolation*, 2013, vol. 54, no. 2, 129-146.

¹³ Isaac Asimov, *I, Robot*, Gnome Press, New York, 1950, 253p.

¹⁴ John Churchill, ‘When the Screens Went Black’, *Maersk Post*, 14 September 2017, <https://careers-origin.maersk.com/home/stories/when-the-screens-went-black>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

¹⁵ For a more detailed discussion, see part 4.

¹⁶ United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, 10 December 1982 Montego Bay, entered into force on 16 November 1994, UNTS vol. 1833, 3; Hereafter LOSC, the Conference itself shall be addressed as “UNCLOS III”.

¹⁷ Jennifer Parker, ‘The Challenges Posed by the Advent of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships for International Maritime Law’, *Australian and New Zealand Maritime Law Journal*, 2021, vol. 35, nr. 1, 31.

¹⁸ Jack Richard Dougherty, ‘Autonomous Vessels are Becoming a Commercial Reality’, *The Maritime Executive*, 24 September 2021, <https://www.maritime-executive.com/editorials/autonomous-vessels-are-becoming-a-commercial-reality>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

¹⁹ Hereafter IMO.

²⁰ For example, with the release of its Interim Guidelines for Autonomous Ship Trials, see IMO MSC, Interim Guidelines for MASS Trials, IMO MSC Circ 1604 of 14 June 2019.

2. A question of terminology

6. Before continuing with the substance of the paper, some clarification should be offered on the terminology that shall be used going forward. In literature, an abundance of terminology exists to describe uncrewed or autonomous vessels:²¹

- Unmanned Surface Vessels (USVs)
- Unmanned Maritime Systems (UMSs, although see also Unmanned Military Systems)²²
- Unmanned Maritime Vehicles (UMVs)
- Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs)
- Unmanned Undersea Vehicles (UUVs)
- Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs)
- Autonomous Marine Vehicles (AMVs)
- Intelligent Ships (in Chinese literature)²³
- Drones (general term used also for aerial, land, naval and underwater systems)²⁴
- etc.

7. Creating clarity in this minefield of terminology was one of the key recommendations of the recent IMO Maritime Safety Committee's regulatory scoping exercise into autonomous and remote-controlled vessels.²⁵ In this document, the IMO adopts the term "Maritime Autonomous Surface Ship" or "MASS" to encompass all levels of remote-controlled and autonomous vessels, regardless of their level of autonomy, size, nature, etc. More specifically, the IMO has defined a MASS as "*a ship which, to a varying degree, can operate independently of human interaction.*"²⁶ For consistency purposes, and to avoid the use of too many terms and concepts, this paper shall do the same.

8. An important distinction may however still be drawn between "remote-controlled" and "autonomous" vessels, the latter being fully autonomous, the other being controlled from either a mother ship or from the land and still having a human in the decision-making loop. Where necessary, a differentiation between both terms may still be made over the course of the paper.

²¹ Supra note 17, Jennifer Parker, 2021, 31; Andrew H. Henderson, 'Murky Waters: The Legal Status of Unmanned Undersea Vehicles', *Naval Law Review*, 2006, vol. 53, 56.

²² See e.g. Michael N. Schmitt & David S. Goddard, 'International Law and the military use of unmanned maritime systems', *International Review of the Red Cross*, 2016, vol. 98, no. 2, 567.

²³ Defined as "ships which automatically perceive and obtain information and data on ship itself, marine environment, logistics and port by making use of sensors, communication, the Internet of Things, the Internet and other technical means, and achieve intelligent operation in terms of ship navigation, management, maintenance and cargo transportation based on computer technology", see Art. 1.1.3, *2015 Rules for Intelligent Ships*, cited in Rui Li, 'On the Legal Status of Unmanned Ships', *China Oceans Law Review*, 2019, no. 4, 167.

²⁴ E.g. Markus Wagner, 'Taking Humans Out of the Loop: Implications for International Humanitarian Law', *Journal of Law Information and Science*, 2011, vol. 21, no. 2, 158.

²⁵ IMO MSC, Outcome of Regulatory Scoping Exercise for the Use of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships, IMO MSC Circ 1638 of 3 June 2021.

²⁶ IMO, *IMO takes first steps to address autonomous ships*, <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/PressBriefings/Pages/08-MS-C-99-MASS-scoping.aspx>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

3. Degrees of Autonomy

9. As stated above, there is still a difference between remote-controlled shipping on the one hand and fully autonomous shipping on the other. Both the IMO and Lloyd’s Registry have attempted to divide the different MASS systems into categories depending on the level of automation and crew:²⁷

	<i>Level of autonomy</i>	<i>Human presence</i>	<i>Operational control</i>	<i>Human role</i>
1	Ship with automated processes and decision support	Yes	Seafarers are on board to operate and control shipboard systems and functions. Some operations may be automated and at times be unsupervised but with seafarers on board ready to take control	Supervision and operation
2	Remotely-controlled with seafarers on board	Yes	The ship is controlled and operated from another location. Seafarers are available on board to take control and to operate the shipboard systems and functions	Backup to manoeuvre, supervise the systems
3	Remotely-controlled without seafarers on board	No	The ship is controlled and operated from another location. There are no seafarers on board	Monitoring and remote control
4	Fully autonomous	No	The operating system of the ship is able to make decisions and determines actions by itself	Monitoring and emergency management

Fig. 2: Four degrees of autonomy as defined by IMO.²⁸

Fig. 3: Categories designed by Lloyd’s Register.²⁹

²⁷ International Maritime Organization (IMO), *Final Reports: Analysis of Regulatory Barriers to the Use of Autonomous Ships*, 18 January 2018, IMO Doc. MSC 99/INF.3.

²⁸ Amit Sharma, Tae-eun Kim & Salman Nazir, ‘Catching up with time? Examining the STCW competence framework for autonomous shipping’, *Ergoship 2019 Conference Paper*, 88.

²⁹ Aristotelis Komianos, ‘The Autonomous Shipping Era. Operational, Regulatory, and Quality Challenges’, *The International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 2018, vol. 12, no. 2, 337.

10. When considering the IMO categories, three stages deal with the automation of certain functions such as operational tasks, situational awareness, etc. Specifically, the first stage contains the use of technology to help the crew perform certain tasks that were traditionally undertaken by humans alone such as radar systems or autopilot. Systems such as these have already been accepted for decades³⁰ and have even been endorsed in earlier conventions or guidelines.³¹

11. The two stages of remote vessels from their end are likely to be – and as will be seen already are – the first kinds of unmanned vessels to set sail, as much of the required technology already exists.³² At these stages, land based crews start to take over the operational functions remotely, while shore-based maintenance staff can undertake the necessary service work.³³ No matter how sophisticated however, ultimate control and responsibility remain with the “crew”, which can interfere with the operations whenever necessary.³⁴

Fig. 4: The two aspects of ship automation.³⁵

Fig. 5: Where to locate the legal challenges?³⁶

12. Stages 2 and 3 show that when the role and responsibility of the crew begin to be altered, legal problems may begin to accumulate (Figure 5).³⁷ In the final stage, when automation is inserted into the decision-making itself, these challenges are magnified. It is only at this final stage one can speak of a truly “autonomous vessel”.³⁸ It should at this phase be stated that while autonomous vessel technologies may one day render ocean navigation a safer enterprise by reducing or removing human error, that day has not yet come, for as stated by Van Hooydonck:

³⁰ The first documents on increased automation were introduced as early as 1964, e.g. IMCO Doc. MSC VIII/11.

³¹ E.g. on the autopilot, SOLAS Reg. V/19.2.8; See also COLREGs Rule 7 (a) and STCW Convention A, Section VIII/2, para. 8.4.

³² Michal Chwedczuk, ‘Analysis of the Legal Status of Unmanned Commercial Vessels in the U.S. Admiralty and Maritime Law’, *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2016, vol. 47, no. 2, 129.

³³ Henrik Ringbom, ‘Regulating Autonomous Ships – Concepts, Challenges and Precedents’, *Ocean Development and International Law*, 2019, vol. 50, no. 2-3, 157.

³⁴ Supra note 33, Henrik Ringbom, 2019, 150-151.

³⁵ Supra note 33, Henrik Ringbom, 2019, 144.

³⁶ Supra note 33, Henrik Ringbom, 2019, 148.

³⁷ Supra note 33, Henrik Ringbom, 2019, 147.

³⁸ Supra note 33, Henrik Ringbom, 2019, 149.

“Anybody who reflects on how immensely difficult it can be for a ship’s master and his pilot to bring a modern sophisticated ship to its berth, will probably think that a transition to fully crewless navigation is hopelessly unrealistic, or simply reject the idea outright as irresponsible, if not morally objectionable.”³⁹

13. As such, even if the arrival of truly robotic ships is a question of “when”, not “if”,⁴⁰ that day has not yet arrived. Therefore, any further discussion utilizing the term MASS shall primarily be considered from the point of view of remote-controlled ships (without an onboard crew). But even remote-controlling vessels this way offers considerable advantages over conventional shipping.

4. Benefits of Automation?

“Without a crew ... and in the absence of need of full crew quarters and design to enable safe movement on board, the autonomous ship will be lighter and cheaper to build. Most passageways for crews will be removed. Crew quarters will be minimized and perhaps even removed. When needed, crew space may be containerized and installed temporarily into the ship. The bridge as conceived in contemporary ships will be smaller and simpler. In addition to saving on crew salaries, there will be savings on crew supplies and energy. The ship will have a slick design and will be equipped with a complex array of sensors and instrumentation. Its design and absence of crew will make it difficult for pirates to board. It will likely be navigated more accurately and consequently with fewer errors, if any, than crewed vessels. It will consume less energy and produce fewer greenhouse gas emissions.”⁴¹

14. When reading the above statement, it almost seems as though MASS promises to offer some kind of international shipping utopia. And while international shipping might be on the eve of a new era, driven by the introduction of advanced technology,⁴² one is left to wonder whether this introduction will lead to improvements over the old situation or total disruptions of what once was.⁴³ In what follows, a number of key advantages resulting from the use of MASS will be discussed, namely: the expected economic benefits, a reduced need for seafarers, the minimization of human-induced accidents and both organizational and design benefits.

³⁹ Eric Van Hooydonck, ‘The Law of Unmanned Merchant Shipping – an Exploration’, *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2014, vol. 20, 405.

⁴⁰ Samantha Jordan, ‘Captain, My Captain: A Look at Autonomous Ships and How They Should Operate under Admiralty Law’, *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review*, 2020, vol. 30, no. 2, 283; Markus Wagner, ‘Taking Humans Out of the Loop: Implications for International Humanitarian Law’, *Journal of Law Information and Science*, 2011, vol. 21, no. 2, 158; Also, Moore’s Law states that computing power and artificial intelligence double every 18-24 months, see Anna Versai, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Moore’s Law’, *Technowize*, 14 May 2017, <https://www.technowize.com/artificial-intelligence-moores-law/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁴¹ Aldo Chircop, ‘Testing International Legal Regimes: The Advent of Automated Commercial Vessels’, *German Yearbook of International Law*, 2018, vol. 60, no. 1, 5.

⁴² *Supra*, note 41, Aldo Chircop, 2018, 1-2.

⁴³ Damilola Osinuga, ‘Unmanned Ships: Coping in the Murky Waters of Traditional Maritime Law’, *Poredbeno Pomorsko Pravo*, 2020, vol. 174, 75.

4.1 Economic Benefits

15. It is fair to say that globalization has been built on international shipping as the lifeblood of the global economy.⁴⁴ Seaborne trade remains to this day the most effective way to move large quantities of goods from country to country.⁴⁵ Since at least 2015, maritime shipping has been carrying approximately 90% of global trade.⁴⁶ As of 2019, the total value of annual world trade shipping has reached over 14 trillion US Dollars,⁴⁷ while approximately 11 billion tons of goods are transported by ship each year.

*Predicted increases in world seaborne trade GDP and population.*⁴⁸

16. Within this trillion dollar industry, the search to keep costs as low as possible is one of the main drivers for innovation.⁴⁹ As crew expenses are generally regarded as the second largest expense in running a ship – behind only fuel costs – it is no surprise crew sizes have been declining for years. Today, large cargo vessels employ upwards of 25 seafarers, costing a shipping company between \$3,000 and \$4,000 per day.⁵⁰ On the military side, an average US Destroyer costs over \$700,000 per day to operate on patrolling missions, whereas a Sea Hunter MASS costs a mere \$15,000 per day to perform the same task.⁵¹

⁴⁴ Jouni Saarni, Sini Nordberg-Davis & Hannu Makkonen, 'From Innovation to Markets-Redefining Shipping', *Remote and Autonomous Ships – The Next Stage*, Rolls-Royce, 2016, 82; Supra note 32, Michal Chwedczuk, 2016, 123.

⁴⁵ Supra note 40, Samantha Jordan, 2020, 284-285.

⁴⁶ International Chamber of Shipping, 'Explaining Shipping', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/explaining/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

⁴⁷ International Chamber of Shipping, 'Shipping and world trade: driving prosperity', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-driving-prosperity/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

⁴⁸ International Chamber of Shipping, <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-driving-prosperity/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁴⁹ Stefan Seltz-Axmacher, 'How One Change to Shipping Goods Could Change the Way We Live', *World Economic Forum*, 6 September 2019, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/09/from-sail-to-self-driving-what-the-history-of-shipping-tells-us-about-the-future-of-autonomous-electric-freight/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

⁵⁰ Evan Ackerman, 'Unmanned Cargo Ships Face Industry Resistance, Are a Good Idea Anyway', *IEEE Spectrum*, 27 February 2014, <https://spectrum.ieee.org/unmanned-cargo-ships-face-industry-resistance-are-a-good-idea-anyway>, last consulted on 11 May 2022; see also Supra note 32, Michal Chwedczuk, 2016, 124-125.

⁵¹ Elrich D. Grome, 'Spectres of the Sea: The United States Navy's Autonomous Ghost Fleet, Its Capabilities and Impacts, and the Legal Ethical Issues That Surround', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 33; see also Supra note 1, Joel Coito, 2021, 284.

4.2 A reduced need for seafarers

17. The average cost of a seafarer is not the only reason for switching towards MASS. With over 50,000 merchant ships trading internationally, an estimated 1,647,500 seafarers currently serve onboard in some capacity. Despite the global demand for seafarers sitting at around 1,545,000, there is already a shortfall of qualified personnel. When isolating the need for officers, a more grim picture begins to appear.⁵²

*The increasing demand for officers and seafarers.*⁵³

18. Despite the growth of international trade, and continuing availability of ratings, the shipping industry has been continuously struggling to find capable officers, with demand greatly exceeding supply. The use of MASS would eliminate this need,⁵⁴ providing an answer to the declining interest in seafarer careers.⁵⁵

⁵² International Chamber of Shipping, 'Shipping and World Trade: Global Supply and Demand for Seafarers', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-global-supply-and-demand-for-seafarers/> last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁵³ The Editorial Team, 'Global supply and demand for seafarers', *Safety4Sea*, 5 February 2018, <https://safety4sea.com/global-supply-demand-seafarers-2/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁵⁴ Raunek Kantharia, 'Can Futuristic Unmanned Cargo Ships Sail Without Seafarers', *Marine Insight*, 11 January 2022, <https://www.marineinsight.com/future-shipping/rolls-royces-futuristic-unmanned-ships-will-sail-without-seafarers/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

⁵⁵ Supra note 41, Aldo Chircop, 5.

19. While commentators like to posit that MASS will allow for a better work-life balance,⁵⁶ it might be rather obvious that seafarers themselves are not as uniformly in favor of the increasing automation. In a survey from Nautilus International, a seafarer's union, 85% of respondents indicated that they believed unmanned, remotely-operated ships posed a threat to safety of life at sea.⁵⁷ Others only see this as the latest attempt in replacing human labor with cheaper machines,⁵⁸ while not all shipping companies are at this moment in favor of the shift towards MASS.⁵⁹ It should be added that at least in the near future (stages 2 and 3) when dealing with remote-controlled MASS, the reduction of onboard seafarers will at least be partially compensated with a necessity for land-based personnel, requiring potentially higher skills and training, which might not be an option for many of today's seafarers.⁶⁰

4.3 No more human-induced accidents

20. If cost reductions and the removal of onboard seafarers are considered as insufficient reasons for making the shift to MASS, a reduction in human-induced incidents can only be applauded. Most commentators agree that MASS technology will improve navigational safety by reducing human errors and incorporating new sensors and technology.⁶¹ In practice, it is true that most marine accidents can in some way be attributed to a human error,⁶² with estimates going from 75% to up to 95% of accidents being caused by a human mistake, often fatigue.⁶³ One such – military related – example was the collision between the USS Fitzgerald and a merchant ship, resulting in the death of seven sailors, clearly demonstrating the potential advantages of a reactive, autonomous vessel (or at least unmanned) vessel.⁶⁴

⁵⁶ Supra note 32, Michal Chwedczuk, 2016, 126.

⁵⁷ X, 'Nautilus urges IMO to take heed of human factors in 'smart ship' review', *Nautilus International*, 9 May 2018, <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/news/nautilus-urges-imo-to-take-heed-of-human-factors-in-smart-ship-review/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁵⁸ George Dvorsky, 'Robots Are Already Replacing Human Workers at an Alarming Rate', *Gizmodo*, 28 March 2017, <https://gizmodo.com/robots-are-already-replacing-human-workers-at-an-alarmi-1793718198>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

⁵⁹ Christian Wienberg, 'Maersk's CEO Can't Imagine Self-Sailing Box Ships in His Lifetime', *Bloomberg Technology*, 15 February 2018, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-02-15/maersk-ceo-can-t-imagine-self-sailing-box-ships-in-his-lifetime>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁶⁰ United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), *Review of Maritime Transport 2019*, UNCTAD/RMT/2019, 83.

⁶¹ Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 'The Legal Status and Operation of Unmanned Maritime Vehicles', *Ocean Development and Coastal Law*, 2018, vol. 50, 40.

⁶² X, 'Ghost Ships', *The Economist*, 8 March 2014, <https://www.economist.com/technology-quarterly/2014/03/06/ghost-ships>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁶³ Sven Gerhard, *Safety and Shipping 1912-2012 From the Titanic to Costa Concordia: An Insurer's Perspective from Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty*, Allianz, 2012, 6.

⁶⁴ The Editorial Team, 'Allianz: Human error behind 75 percent of marine casualties', *Safety4Sea*, 25 August 2017, <https://safety4sea.com/allianz-human-error-behind-75-percent-of-marine-casualties/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022; Elrich D. Grome, 'Spectres of the Sea: The United States Navy's Autonomous Ghost Fleet, Its Capabilities and Impacts, and the Legal Ethical Issues That Surround', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 34; Max Greenwood, '7 sailors missing in ship collision found dead', *The Hill*, 27 June 2017, <https://thehill.com/policy/defense/338307-seven-sailors-missing-in-ship-collision-found-dead/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

1	Human error	75%
2	Accidental nature/damage	18%
3	Natural hazards	1%
4	Negligence/poor maintenance	<1%
5	Failure to provide service	<1%
6	Other	5%

Reasons for shipping accidents.⁶⁵

21. No system is perfect however and to this day, avoiding collisions in highly dynamic areas, such as bustling ports, is one field where humans still have the edge on sensor systems.⁶⁶ While future autonomous integrated systems might indeed be safer than humans, unfazed as they are by fatigue or distractions, technology has not yet reached this level of advancement.⁶⁷

4.4 Organizational Benefits

22. One area where MASS already excel is their organizational flexibility. Not only can they be deployed for longer⁶⁸ and operate more stealthily (from a military perspective),⁶⁹ they also remove the need to involve humans in “dull, dangerous or dirty” jobs.⁷⁰ Finally, in case of conflicts, disputes or accidents involving MASS, national populations might be less inclined to demand answers or retaliation, thus reducing the pressure on national governments as well as chances of escalation.⁷¹ From a law enforcement perspective, MASS could aid governments in reaching Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA)⁷² via the use of an advanced array of sensor technology superior to the human eye and capabilities,⁷³ thus increasing efficiency and options.⁷⁴

⁶⁵ Andrew Russ, ‘The human element – the effects of fatigue on ship safety’, Safety4Sea, 3 July 2018, <https://safety4sea.com/the-human-element-the-effects-of-fatigue-on-ship-safety/>, last consulted 14 May 2022.

⁶⁶ Supra note 10, Paul W. Pritchett, 2015, 202.

⁶⁷ Supra note 40, Samantha Jordan, 2020, 286; see also supra note 39, quote by Eric Van Hooydonck, 2014, 405.

⁶⁸ Natalie Klein, ‘Maritime Autonomous Vehicles within the International Law Framework to Enhance Maritime Security’, *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2019, vol. 95, 246.

⁶⁹ Simon McKenzie, ‘When is a Ship a Ship? Use by State Armed Forces of Uncrewed Maritime Vehicles and the United Nations Convention on the Law the Sea’, *Melbourne Journal of International Law*, 2020, vol. 21, no. 2, 376.

⁷⁰ Stephanie Showalter, ‘The Legal Status of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles’, *Marine Technology & Society Journal*, 2004, vol. 38, no. 1, 80.

⁷¹ Rob McLaughlin, ‘Unmanned Naval Vehicles at Sea: USVs, UUVs and the Adequacy of the Law’, *Journal of Law, Information and Science*, 2011, vol. 21, 114.

⁷² Defined as “the effective understanding of any activity associated with the maritime environment that could impact upon ... security, safety, economy or the environment”, see Amendments to the International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue (IAMSAR) Manual Annex 11, IMO Doc. MSC.1/Circ. 1415, 25 May 2012.

⁷³ X, ‘Unmanned Vehicles Could Aid Search and Rescue’, *The Maritime Executive*, 16 December 2016, <https://www.maritime-executive.com/editorials/unmanned-vehicles-could-aid-search-and-rescue>, last consulted on 14 May 2022; R. Glenn Wright, ‘Intelligent Autonomous Ship Navigation Using Multi-sensor Modalities’, *International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 2019, vol. 13, 505.

⁷⁴ Douglas Guilfoyle, ‘Maritime Law Enforcement Operations and Intelligence in an Age of Maritime Security’, *International Law Studies*, 2017, vol. 93, 300.

4.5 Design Benefits

23. A final area where MASS offer benefits beyond what it possible for conventional shipping is in their design and the consequences this brings. Firstly, a redesigned ship will allow for the removal of human-supporting infrastructure, thus reducing weight fuel consumption.⁷⁵ Be not having to worry about humans onboard, ships can also be designed as efficiently as possible, thus reducing potential ship resistance and improving the efficiency of propulsion, leading to a reduction in energy necessity, fuel consumption and eventually a reduction of emissions,⁷⁶ while allowing for more cargo to be transported.⁷⁷

24. The inclusion of more automated systems does come with risks as well though, for as was already made clear by the 2017 MAERSK cyberattack,⁷⁸ new challenges arise in the form of cybersecurity.⁷⁹

5. The evolution towards unmanned and autonomous shipping

25. These benefits and challenges have been driving the increasing use of MASS for years, and to a certain extent even centuries. In what follows, a brief overview of MASS development and current uses will be offered, completing the reader's view of this growing industry, before moving to the most pressing legal challenge of at this moment.

5.1 From humble military Beginnings ...

26. if one is looking for the origins of MASS, one might go back to as far as 200 BC when commanders employed unmanned vessels in sea warfare to gain a military advantage over their opponents while minimizing their soldiers' exposure to the risks of combat.⁸⁰ These "fireships" would be set ablaze and left to sail in the adversary's direction, before exploding.⁸¹ Fast-forward a couple of centuries and the industrial revolution has given birth to self-propelled and self-guided underwater explosives or torpedoes, used during the Crimean and US Civil War.⁸² It was not until 1892 however, that the first true small-scale MASSs saw the light of day, when Nicola Tesla demonstrated the potential of his remote controlled boats to the US Navy.⁸³

⁷⁵ Supra note 10, Paul W. Pritchett, 2015, 201.

⁷⁶ Damilola Osinuga, 'Unmanned Ships: Coping in the Murky Waters of Traditional Maritime Law', *Poredbeno Pomorsko Pravo*, 2020, vol. 174, 79.

⁷⁷ Supra note 32, Michal Chwedczuk, 2016, 126.

⁷⁸ Supra note 14, John Churchill, 'When the Screens Went Black', 14 September 2017.

⁷⁹ Kimberly Tam & Kevin Jones, 'Cyber-Risk Assessment for Autonomous Ships', *Cyber Security*, Conference Paper, May 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325195302_Cyber-Risk_Assessment_for_Autonomous_Ships.

⁸⁰ Brendan Gogarty & Meredith Hagger, 'The Laws of Man over Vehicles Unmanned: The Legal Response to Robotic Revolution on Sea, Land and Air', *Journal of Law, Information and Science*, 2008, vol. 19, 71.

⁸¹ Alexander Gillespie, *A History of the Laws of War Vol. 3*, 2011, Hart Publishing, Oxford | Portland, 27.

⁸² Hitoshi Nasu & David Letts, 'The Legal Characterization of Lethal Autonomous Maritime Systems: Warship, Torpedo, or Naval Mine?', *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2020, vol. 96, 80.

⁸³ Craig H. Allen, 'Determining the Legal Status of Unmanned Maritime Vehicles: Formalism vs Functionalism', *Journal of Maritime and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 4, 483.

27. This potential would later be used by the German Empire during WW1, which would use “Fernlenkboten”, loaded with explosives and controlled via cable to ram British warships.⁸⁴

German FL-boat during WWI.⁸⁵

28. Today, the military sphere is probably the area where interest MASS has been the most extensive. In 2010, The US’ Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) launched its Continuous Trail Unmanned Vessel (ACTUV) program, seeking to develop a frigate-sized MASS meant for independent global operations.⁸⁶ These plans were later expanded in search of the creation of an entire “ghost fleet” of MASSs.⁸⁷ The goal of this new surface fighting force is to reduce risk for sailors and combatants, provide an answer for waning interest in a naval career, as well as broadening the US military’s reach at a reduced cost.⁸⁸ By 2018, efforts had borne fruit as the first Sea Hunter was released for operational testing, while the University of Southern Mississippi was tasked with providing courses to the MASS operators.⁸⁹

⁸⁴ Supra note 83, Craig H. Allen, 2018, 483.

⁸⁵ X, ‘German Explosive Remote-Control speedboats of WW1 and WW2’, *Standing Well Back, IED & EOD Evolutions*, <https://www.standingwellback.com/german-explosive-remote-control-speedboats-of-ww1-and-ww2/>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

⁸⁶ Alexander M. G. Walan, ‘Anti-Submarine Warfare (ASW) Continuous Trail Unmanned Vessel (ACTUV)’, *Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency*, 2010, <https://www.darpa.mil/program/anti-submarine-warfare-continuous-trail-unmanned-vessel>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁸⁷ Sam LaGrone, ‘Navy Wants 10-Ship Unmanned “Ghost Fleet” to supplement Manned Force’, *USNI News*, 13 March 2019, <https://news.usni.org/2019/03/13/navy-wants-ten-ship-3b-unmanned-experimental-ghost-fleet>, last consulted 13 May 2022; Kris Osborn, ‘The Navy’s Future Swarm Ghost Fleet’, *Real Clear Defense*, 1 February 2017, www.realcleardefense.com/2017/02/02/the_navy039s_future_swarm_quotghost_fleetquot_290008.html, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁸⁸ Elrich D. Grome, ‘Spectres of the Sea: The United States Navy’s Autonomous Ghost Fleet, Its Capabilities and Impacts, and the Legal Ethical Issues That Surround’, *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 31; Kris Osborn, ‘The Navy’s Future Swarm Ghost Fleet’, *Real Clear Defense*, 1 February 2017, https://www.realcleardefense.com/2017/02/02/the_navy039s_future_swarm_quotghost_fleetquot_290008.html, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁸⁹ Supra note 83, Craig H. Allen, 2018, 478; see also Ronald O’Rourke, ‘Navy Large Unmanned Surface and Undersea Vehicles: Background and Issues for Congress’, *Congressional Research Service*, 11 May 2022, summary.

Picture of an Israeli Protector small-scale MASS.⁹⁰

Picture of the American Sea Hunter MASS (crewed for testing purposes).⁹¹

29. The US is not alone in pursuing this development however. The Chinese “Haiyan” can operate at depths of up to 1,000 meters, travel at 4 knots, and sustain operations (surveillance, minesweeping, anti-surface warfare, etc.) for a month.⁹² Similarly, the Russian military has chosen to invest in a new form of “nuclear delivery drone” capable of transporting a nuclear payload up to 6,200 nautical miles deep, at a speed of over 50 knots⁹³ Finally, the Israeli Protector is a nine-meter MASS that can travel at a speed of 50 knots and has a set of human-controlled machine guns.⁹⁴ It was specifically designed to protect against seaborne terrorist attacks.⁹⁵

⁹⁰ N. R. P., ‘Top 10 Most Powerful Weapons of The Israeli Military’, *Defencyclopedia*, 30 January 2015, <https://defencyclopedia.com/2015/01/30/top-10-most-powerful-weapons-of-the-israeli-military/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁹¹ X, ‘Sea Hunter’, *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sea_Hunter, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

⁹² DoD, Defense Science Board, Summer Study on autonomy, 2016, 43, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/AD1017790>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁹³ Kyle Mizokami, ‘Pentagon Confirms Russia Has a Submarine Nuke Delivery Drone’, *Popular Mechanics*, 8 December 2016, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/weapons/a24216/pentagon-confirm-russia-submarine-nuke/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

⁹⁴ X, ‘Protector USV’, *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Protector_USV, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

⁹⁵ See Erik Sofge, ‘Robot Boats Hunt High-Tech Pirates on the High-Speed Seas’, *Popular Mechanics*, 2 October 2009, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/navy-ships/a2234/4229443/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

30. As such, while the technology for some form of automated transport has been available for many years now,⁹⁶ it is only more recent developments that have caught the broader public's eye and led to an increasing diversification in the use of MASS.⁹⁷

5.2 To greatly varied uses ...

31. While initial development of MASS was indeed primarily driven by military application, the civilian world has now begun taking an interest as well.⁹⁸ The author should be careful however, as the absence of a crew is not a new phenomenon per se and unmanned towed barges and small-scale submersibles have long been in civilian use as well.⁹⁹ Small unmanned MASS especially have – for decades now – been used in situations of nuclear radiation,¹⁰⁰ in exploring and preparing exploitation of nonliving subsea resources,¹⁰¹ as well as the discovery of shipwrecks such as the Titanic and the Bismarck.¹⁰² On a more recent note, they have also found use in oil spill removal,¹⁰³ marine resource surveys,¹⁰⁴ marine research¹⁰⁵ and from a more clandestine perspective, drug trafficking.¹⁰⁶

32. What has really given the impetus for legal research however, have been the recent attempts of shipping companies to use MASS for the large scale shipping of goods.¹⁰⁷ Examples are legion, from Hyundai seeking to acquire an autonomous LNG-carrier,¹⁰⁸ to the 54 meter long Rolls-Royce Falco Fully Autonomous Ferry¹⁰⁹ and the EU-sponsored AUTOSHIP-project.¹¹⁰

⁹⁶ E.g. United States Patent Office, 'Letter of Patent no. 613809 – Method of and Apparatus for Controlling Mechanism of Moving Vehicle of Vehicles', Nicholas Tesla, 8 November 1898.)

⁹⁷ Paul David, 'From Automation to Autonomy – Can the Law Keep up?', *Australian and New Zealand Maritime Law Journal*, 2020, vol. 34, no. 1, 6.

⁹⁸ Supra note 10, Paul W. Pritchett, 2015, 197.

⁹⁹ Supra note 41, Aldo Chircop, 2018, 2.

¹⁰⁰ Supra note 22, Michael N. Schmitt & David S. Goddard, 2016, 570.

¹⁰¹ Supra note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 23.

¹⁰² Supra note 21, Andrew H. Henderson, 2006, 57.

¹⁰³ M. Wingrove, 'Autonomy Tested for Oil Spill Removal', *Riviera Maritime Media*, 7 January 2020, <https://www.rivieramm.com/news-content-hub/news-content-hub/autonomy-tested-for-oil-spill-removal-57354>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

¹⁰⁴ X, 'Detecting Fish From Ocean-Going Robots To Complement Ship-Based Surveys', NOAA Fisheries News, 22 August 2019, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/feature-story/detecting-fish-ocean-going-robots-complement-ship-based-surveys>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

¹⁰⁵ Daniel F. Carlson, Alexander Fürsterling, e.a., 'An affordable and portable autonomous surface vehicle with obstacle avoidance for coastal ocean monitoring', *Hardware X*, April 2019, vol. 5, article e00059.

¹⁰⁶ Supra note 1, Joel Coito, 2021, 278.

¹⁰⁷ X, 'NYK Conducts World's First Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships Trial', *NYK News Release*, 30 September 2019, https://www.nyk.com/english/news/2019/20190930_01.html, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

¹⁰⁸ The Maritime Executive, 'Hyundai Plans First Ocean-Going Autonomous Ship voyage by Year's End', *The Maritime Executive*, 27 July 2021, <https://www.maritime-executive.com/article/hyundai-plans-first-ocean-going-autonomous-ship-voyage-by-year-s-end>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

¹⁰⁹ X, 'Rolls-Royce and Finferries demonstrate world's first Fully Autonomous Ferry', *Rolls Royce*, 3 December 2018, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/2018/03-12-2018-rr-and-finferries-demonstrate-worlds-first-fully-autonomous-ferry.aspx>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

¹¹⁰ European Commission, *Autonomous Shipping Initiative for European Waters*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815012>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

33. Efforts by industrial leaders such as Rolls-Royce, Kongsberg, Yara, Inmarsat and Wilhelmsen have not only aided in making autonomous ships a reality,¹¹¹ but also in showing the remainder of the sector the disruptive potential of these new technologies.¹¹² Especially famous is the Yara Birkeland autonomous and fully electric cargo MASS, the origins of which go back to 2012 as Rolls-Royce began developing plans for different kinds of remote-controlled cargo MASS for transporting cargo¹¹³ and people.¹¹⁴

*The Yara Birkeland.*¹¹⁵

34. Rapid advances over the past years show that MASS may indeed revolutionize personal and commercial transportation as it is known today.¹¹⁶ While small MASS will continue to have their uses both in the military and in certain niche roles, research is now aimed at the creation of ever larger MASS for the transport of either cargo or people.¹¹⁷ This development raises challenging questions on how these vehicles fit within the existing framework of ocean governance. In what follows, the consequences for international law of these technological evolutions will be discussed to determine whether, new regulation is necessary or not.¹¹⁸

¹¹¹ Inmarsat Partners with Rolls Royce on Autonomous Ship Project, *Inmarsat*, 8 September 2015, <https://www.inmarsat.com/en/news/latest-news/maritime/2015/inmarsat-partners-with-rolls-royce-on-autonomous-ship-project.html>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

¹¹² *Supra* note 97, Paul David, 2020, 3.

¹¹³ Isaac Arnsdorf, 'Rolls-Royce Drone Ships Challenge \$375 Billion Industry: Freight', *Bloomberg Business*, 25 February 2014, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2014-02-25/rolls-royce-drone-ships-challenge-375-billion-industry-freight>, last consulted on 12 May 2022; see also *supra* note 97, Paul David, 2020, 5.

¹¹⁴ Danielle Sullivan Kaminski, 'Who's to Blame When no one is Manning the Ship?', *Law360*, 6 October 2016, <https://www.law360.com/articles/847478>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

¹¹⁵ X, 'AUTONOMOUS SHIP PROJECT, KEY FACTS ABOUT YARA BIRKELAND', *Kongsberg*, <https://www.kongsberg.com/maritime/support/themes/autonomous-ship-project-key-facts-about-yara-birkeland/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

¹¹⁶ Jeremy A. Carp, 'Autonomous Vehicles: Problems and Principles for future Regulation', *University of Pennsylvania Journal of Law and Public Affairs*, 2018, vol. 4, 84.

¹¹⁷ Andrzej Felski & Karolina Zwolak, 'the Ocean-Going Autonomous Ship: Challenges and threats', *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 2020, vol. 8, 41.

¹¹⁸ *Supra* note 68, Natalie Klein, 2019, 245.

6. Can a MASS be considered a ship or vessel?

35. Having given the necessary framework on the evolution of MASS, the core legal question now needs to be answered: *“To what degree can MASS be considered ships or vessels?”* The uncertainty on a definition of the term “ship” has been ongoing since at least the First Law of the Sea Conference in 1958, when the International Law Commission (ILC) attempted to draft a definition, but failed to reach agreement, primarily as a result of uncertainty due to non-self-propelled barges.¹¹⁹ Since then, there has been no internationally uniform definition of a “ship”.¹²⁰ As such, whether MASS constitute a ship or vessel has been the subject of much ink to this day.¹²¹

6.1 Ship or Vessel?

36. The first problem one encounters on this journey is the seemingly random use of the terms “ship” and “vessel” throughout the LOSC, the constitution of the oceans,¹²² as well as other international treaties. Usually, these terms are used in circular definitions referring to one another. As to the question whether there is a difference between these terms, one can be brief however. The 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (hereafter VCLT) states that *“A treaty shall be interpreted in good faith in accordance with the ordinary meaning to be given to the terms of the treaty in their context and in the light of its object and purpose.”*¹²³ Art. 32 VCLT furthermore adds the possibility of consulting the preparatory works of a treaty, while art. 33 (1) states that *“When a treaty has been authenticated in two or more languages, the text is equally authoritative in each language.”*

37. Taking the above into consideration, it was clearly the intention of the parties not to give a different meaning to the terms “ship” and “vessel” under the LOSC, but they were rather meant to be used as synonyms.¹²⁴ Their interchangeable use throughout the LOSC (and other treaties) supports this argument.¹²⁵ Finally, taking art. 33 (1) VCLT into account, the French and Spanish authentic versions of the LOSC use only a single term instead of two, namely “navire” and “buque” respectively.¹²⁶ In what follows both terms shall therefore equally be considered interchangeable.

¹¹⁹ See I. G. Gidel, *Le Droit International Public De La Met*, 70 (1934).

¹²⁰ Richard Shaw, ‘What is a Ship in Maritime Law?’, *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2005, vol. 11, 247.

¹²¹ Gotthard Mark Gauci, ‘Is it a Vessel, a Ship of a Boat, is it Just a Craft, or is it Merely a Contrivance’, *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2016, vol. 47, 479; see also Andrew H. Henderson, ‘Murky Waters: The Legal Status of Unmanned Undersea Vehicles’, *Naval Law Review*, 2006, vol. 53, 59.

¹²² Tommy T. B. Koh, *A Constitution of the Oceans*, 6 and 11 December 1982, Montego Bay, http://www.un.org/Depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/koh_english.pdf, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

¹²³ Art. 31 (1) Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 23 May 1969, UNTC vol. 1155, 331.

¹²⁴ UN Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea, *Navigation on the High Seas: Legislative History of Part VII, Section (Articles 87, 89, 90-94, 96-98) of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea*, at 80, UN Sales No. E.89.V2 (1989).

¹²⁵ UNCLOS III, Report of the Chairman of the Drafting Committee, UN Doc. A/CONF.62/L.40 (1980), OR XIII, 97; see also Oliver Daim, ‘The Implications of International Law on Unmanned Naval Craft’, *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 75.

¹²⁶ *Supra* note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 383.

6.2 The Silence of the LOSC

38. Whether MASS can be considered ships under the 1982 LOSC is a question of significant importance.¹²⁷ The rights and duties that MASS will have or be forced to comply with will largely be a result of this classification.¹²⁸ For example, under articles 24 (1) (b) and 42 (2) LOSC, States may not discriminate against “ships” or any State. If MASS are not ships, these articles would be of no use in their situation. More importantly, the regimes of innocent passage¹²⁹ and the right of navigation¹³⁰ are awarded to ships, not to other vehicles. In general, categorizing a MASS as a ship or vessel leads to crucial consequences for its rights and obligations under the LOSC.¹³¹ In what follows, the question of whether a MASS can be considered a ship shall be treated both from a more textual point of view and from a more evolutionary perspective.

6.2.1 The Text of the Convention

39. The first way of interpreting whether MASS can be considered ships or vessels is by applying the already mentioned art. 31 (1) VCLT to determine the parties’ objective intention via a good faith interpretation of the text of the treaty.¹³² In this regard, nothing in the Convention outright prohibits MASS as being considered ships for its purposes and art. 91 (1) on the nationality of ships awards the flag State broad discretion in determining whether to grant its nationality to a “ship”, potentially leading to a plethora of interpretations.¹³³ There are however a number of provisions that seem to suggest that ships under the LOSC should always be manned.

40. Firstly, art. 94 (4) (b) states that the flag State must ensure that “... *each ship is in the charge of a master and officers who possess appropriate qualifications, in particular in seamanship, navigation, communications and marine engineering, and that the crew is appropriate in qualification and numbers for the type, size, machinery and equipment of the ship*”. There is little question that art. 94 LOSC was drafted with conventionally crewed ships in mind.¹³⁴ However, a different argument could also be made, namely that it is nowhere explicitly mentioned that the crew and master should be aboard the ship while operating it and it has indeed been posited that this mandate could in the future be met via shore-based operators.¹³⁵

¹²⁷ Supra note 83, Craig H. Allen, 2018, 480.

¹²⁸ Supra note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 25.

¹²⁹ Art. 17 LOSC.

¹³⁰ Art. 90 LOSC.

¹³¹ J. Ashley Roach, ‘Today’s Customary International Law of the Sea’, *Ocean Development and International Law*, 2014, vol. 45, no. 3, 239; see also Robert Veal et al., ‘The Legal Status and Operation of Unmanned Maritime Vehicles’, *Ocean Development and International Law*, 2019, vol. 50, 25-31; Anthony Morrison & Stuart Kaye, ‘Operating Unmanned Surface Vessels at Sea: Is International Law Ready for the Future?’ in Myron Nordquist, John Moore & Ronan Long (eds.), *Legal Order in the World’s Oceans*, Brill Nijhoff, 2017, 424, 438.

¹³² Supra note 83, Craig H. Allen, 2018, 477; Supra note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 383.

¹³³ Supra note 39, Eric Van Hooydonck, 2014, 410.

¹³⁴ Supra note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 387; see also supra note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 27.

¹³⁵ Supra note 40, Samantha Jordan, 2020, 296.

41. A different argument is made in the context of the duty of search and rescue as contained in art. 98 LOSC under which a flag State shall require the master of a ship to:

“(a) to render assistance to any person found at sea in danger of being lost;

(b) to proceed with all possible speed to the rescue of persons in distress, if informed of their need of assistance, in so far as such action may reasonably be expected of him ...”¹³⁶

This provisions seems problematic based on the earlier discussed design changes in MASS.¹³⁷ After all, while a shore-based master might indeed be able to navigate towards the persons in distress, if the ship does not have any hallways, cabins or human-supporting infrastructure or people on board, how to offer help to those in need?¹³⁸

42. A final argument can be made when looking at the definition of a warship in art. 29 LOSC which specifically mentions the presence of an officer and a crew. This definition originated in the 1907 Hague Convention VII relating to the Conversion of Merchant Ships into Warships¹³⁹ and was passed on to the LOSC via the 1958 Geneva Convention on the High Seas.¹⁴⁰ Today the definition is considered as part of customary international law.¹⁴¹ While many future MASS will be of a commercial and not a military nature, it can nonetheless be posited that the drafters of the LOSC were simply giving a militarized definition of what they considered to be the necessary qualities of a ship under the Convention.

43. What these three specific arguments show, is that MASSs were not considered at the time of drafting the LOSC and the Convention and its rights and obligations seem written for manned ships only. The IMO itself recognized in its scoping exercise that the LOSC does not currently seem adequate to regulate MASS in the maritime domain.¹⁴² Not all authors agree however, Rui Li does believe that MASS meet the criteria of ships under the LOSC,¹⁴³ while Veal, Tsimplis and Serdy believe it was not the intention of the LOSC drafters to exclude the applicability of the Convention to new technologies if these could be fitted into the object and purpose of the Convention.¹⁴⁴ To determine whether the LOSC could indeed cope with these systems, a more evolutionary interpretation is however required.

¹³⁶ Art. 98 (1) (a) & (b) LOSC.

¹³⁷ Supra Part 4.5.

¹³⁸ Supra note 40, Samantha Jordan, 2020, 315.

¹³⁹ Arts. 1-4, Convention VII relating to the Conversion of Merchant Ships into WarShips, 18 October 1907.

¹⁴⁰ Art. 8 (2) Convention on the High Seas, 29 April 1958, 450 UNTS 11.

¹⁴¹ Supra note 22, Michael N. Schmitt & David S. Goddard, 2016, 579.

¹⁴² Legal Committee of the International Maritime Organization, 108th Session, LEG 108, 26-30 July 2021; See also supra note 17, Jennifer Parker, 2021, 36.

¹⁴³ Rui Li, ‘On the Legal Status of Unmanned Ships’, *China Oceans Law Review*, 2019, no. 4, 173.

¹⁴⁴ Supra note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 27.

6.2.2 An evolutionary interpretation?

“... the international law of the sea is not a mere static body of rules but is rather a whole decision-making process, ... It is, in other words, a process of continuous interaction, of continuous demand and response, ... As such a process, it is a living, growing law, grounded in the practices and sanctioning expectations of nation-state officials, and changing as their demands and expectations are changed by the exigencies of new interests and technology and by other continually evolving conditions in the world arena.”¹⁴⁵

44. While the LOSC might have had as its ambition to serve as a constitution of the oceans,¹⁴⁶ it remains a product of its time and will therefore undoubtedly face interpretative challenges in the modern era.¹⁴⁷ The Preamble does reveal the parties’ high hopes however, referring to how the Convention sought to settle all issues relating to the law of the sea,¹⁴⁸ recognizing that all these issues are closely interrelated¹⁴⁹ and how the LOSC sought to strengthen peace and security via codification and progressive development.¹⁵⁰ Taking into account the package-deal approach¹⁵¹ and framework nature of the Convention,¹⁵² this idea of progressive development becomes especially interesting.

45. The idea of an evolutionary interpretation is nothing new either. In the *Namibia Advisory Opinion*, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) stated that every treaty “*must be interpreted and applied within the framework of the entire legal system prevailing at the time of the interpretation.*”¹⁵³ The Court made similar reasonings in *Aegean Sea Continental Shelf*,¹⁵⁴ *Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project*¹⁵⁵ and *Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay*.¹⁵⁶

¹⁴⁵ Myres S. McDougal, ‘The Hydrogen Bomb Tests and the International Law of the Sea’ (1955) 49 *AJIL* 356, 356–7, cited in Natalie Klein, *Maritime Security and the Law of the Sea*, Oxford University Press, 2011, 301.

¹⁴⁶ *Supra* note 122, Tommy T. B. Koh.

¹⁴⁷ Matt Bartlett, ‘Game of Drones: Unmanned Maritime Vehicles and the Law of the Sea’, *Auckland University Law Review*, 2018, vol. 24, 67.

¹⁴⁸ Preamble para. 1.

¹⁴⁹ Preamble para. 3.

¹⁵⁰ Preamble para. 7.

¹⁵¹ *supra* Peter J. Cook & Chris M. Carleton, 2000, 8; Jing Geng, ‘The Legality of Foreign Military Activities in the Exclusive Economic Zone and under UNCLOS’, *Merkourios* 2012, vol. 28, Issue 74, p. 22–30, 25; Richard J. Grunawalt ‘Freedom of Navigation in the Post-Cold War Era’ in Donald R. Rothwell and Sam Bateman, *Navigational Rights and Freedoms and the New Law of the Sea*, Martinus Nijhoff, The Hague/London, 2000, 16.

¹⁵² Cdr. James Kraska, U.S. Navy, ‘Resource rights and Environmental Protection in the Exclusive Economic Zone: the Functional Approach to Naval Operations’ in Peter A. Dutton (ed.), *Military Activities in the EEZ: A U.S.–China dialogue on Security and International Law in the Maritime commons*, Naval War College/China Maritime Studies Institute No. 7, 2010, 75; *Supra*, James Kraska, 2011, 100.

¹⁵³ *Legal Consequences for States of the Continued Presence of South Africa in Namibia (South West Africa) Notwithstanding Security Council Resolution 276 (1970)*, ICJ Advisory Opinion, 21 June 1971, para. 53.

¹⁵⁴ *Aegean Sea Continental Shelf* (Greece v. Turkey), ICJ Judgement, 19 December 1978, para. 77.

¹⁵⁵ *Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project* (Hungary v. Slovakia), ICJ Judgement, 25 September 1997, para. 140.

¹⁵⁶ *Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay* (Argentina v. Uruguay), ICJ Judgement, 20 April 2010, para. 204.

46. Furthermore, where the Court has found that such an evolutionary interpretation – rather than a textual or original meaning – is especially defensible in case a generic term, such as ship or vessel, is used. In the *Dispute regarding Navigational and Related Rights*, the Court stated that:

*“Where the parties have used generic terms in a treaty, the parties necessarily having been aware that the meaning of the terms was likely to evolve over time, and where the treaty has been entered into for a very long period or is ‘of continuing duration’, the parties must be presumed, as a general rule, to have intended those terms to have an evolving meaning.”*¹⁵⁷

47. Taking the abovementioned into account, the lack of an explicit refusal to include MASS from the scope of “ship” or “vessel”, the goals of the Convention, the evolution of technology and the views of different States as well as other Instruments and Treaties,¹⁵⁸ it is only logical to conclude that MASSs can indeed be considered vessels – at least – for the purposes of the LOSC. The many doctrinal sources collected in pursuing an answer to this question point in a similar direction and agree that the lack of an onboard crew does not fundamentally change the nature of a ship.¹⁵⁹

6.3 Overwhelmed by the IMO

48. If the LOSC fails to offer sufficient definitions or support to determine the meaning of a “ship”, the many instruments adopted within the context of the IMO seemingly offer too many. The following table gives a – non-exhaustive – indication:

Instrument	Definition of ship or vessel
COLREGs ¹⁶⁰	Rule 3 (a): <i>“every description of water craft, including non-displacement craft and seaplanes used or capable of being used as a means of transportation on water.”</i>
SOLAS ¹⁶¹	No single definition, art. 2 refers back to national laws while multiple regulations contain multiple definitions.
MARPOL ¹⁶²	Art. 2 (4): <i>“a vessel of any type whatsoever operating in the marine environment and includes hydrofoil boats, air-cushion vehicles, submersibles, floating craft and fixed or floating platforms.”</i>

¹⁵⁷ *Dispute regarding Navigational and Related Rights* (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), ICJ Judgement, 13 July 2009, para. 66.

¹⁵⁸ *Infra* Parts 6.3 & 6.4; As will be seen, the fact that other treaties sometimes offer more restrictive definitions of a “ship”, also points in the direction that States could already have limited the definition at the time, should they have wanted to, see *Supra* note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 392.

¹⁵⁹ *Supra* note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 27; also *supra* note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 373 & 401

¹⁶⁰ Convention on the international regulations for preventing collisions at sea, 20 October 1972, UNTC vol. 1050, 16..

¹⁶¹ International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea, 1974, 1 November 1974, UNTC vol. 1184-1185, 2.

¹⁶² International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships, as amended by the 1978 Protocol, 17 February 1978, UNTC vol. 1340, 61.

UN Convention on the Registration of Ships ¹⁶³	Art. 2: <i>“any self-propelled seagoing vessel used in international seaborne trade for the transport of goods, passengers, or both.”</i>
London Dumping Convention ¹⁶⁴	Art. III (2): <i>“‘Vessels and Aircraft’ means waterborne or airborne craft of any type whatsoever. This expression includes air cushioned craft and floating craft, whether self-propelled or not.”</i>
Salvage Convention ¹⁶⁵	Art. 1 (b): <i>“Vessel means any ship or craft, or any structure capable of navigation.”</i>
Nairobi Convention ¹⁶⁶	Art. 1 (2): <i>“... a seagoing vessel of any type whatsoever and includes hydrofoil boats, air-cushion vehicles , submersibles, floating craft ... except when such platforms are on location engaged in the exploration, exploitation or production of seabed mineral resources.”</i>
Athens Convention ¹⁶⁷	Art. 1 (3): <i>“‘ship’ means only a seagoing vessel, excluding an air-cushion vehicle.”</i>
Oil Pollution Casualties Convention ¹⁶⁸	Art. II (2): <i>“(a) any sea-going vessel of any type whatsoever, and (b) any floating craft, with the exception of an installation or device engaged in the exploration and exploitation of the resources of the sea-bed and the ocean floor and the subsoil thereof ...”</i>
Civil Liability Convention ¹⁶⁹	Art. I.1: <i>“‘Ship’ means any sea-going vessel and sea-borne craft of any type whatsoever constructed or adapted for the carriage oil in bulk as cargo, provided that a ship capable of carrying oil and other cargoes shall be regarded as a ship only when it is actually carrying oil in bulk as cargo and during any voyage following such carriage unless it is proved that it has no residues of such carriage in bulk aboard.”</i>
Oil Pollution Fund Convention ¹⁷⁰	Art. I (2): <i>“... same meaning as in Article I of the Liability Convention ...”</i>
HNS Convention ¹⁷¹	Art. 1 (1): <i>“Ship means any seagoing vessel and seaborne craft, of any type whatsoever.”</i>

¹⁶³ United Nations Convention on Conditions for Registration of Ships, 7 February 1968 (not yet in force), UN Doc. TD/RS/CONF/19/Add.1.

¹⁶⁴ Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter, 1046 UNTS 138, 29 December 1972; See also Art. 1 (6) Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes or Other Matter, 7 November 1996.

¹⁶⁵ International Convention on Salvage, 28 April 1989, UNTC vol. 1953, 165.

¹⁶⁶ Nairobi International Convention on the removal of wrecks, 18 May 2007, UNTC vol. no. not available, see <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=080000028053c3a0>.

¹⁶⁷ Athens Convention Relating to the Carriage of Passengers and their Luggage by Sea, 13 December 1974, UNTC vol. 1463, 20.

¹⁶⁸ International Convention relating to intervention on the high seas in cases of oil pollution casualties, 29 November 1969, UNTC vol. 970, 211.

¹⁶⁹ International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage, 29 November 1969, UNTC vol. 973, 3.

¹⁷⁰ International Convention on the establishment of an international fund for compensation for oil pollution damage, 18 December 1971, UNTC vol. 1110, 57.

¹⁷¹ International Convention on Liability and Compensation for Damage in Connection with the Carriage of Hazardous and Noxious Substances by Sea, 2 May 1996, not yet in force.

1962 Amendments on oil pollution ¹⁷²	Art. 1 (1): <i>“any seagoing vessel of any type whatsoever, including floating craft, whether self-propelled or towed by another vessel, making a sea voyage”.</i>
OPRC Convention ¹⁷³	Art. 2 (3): <i>“... a vessel of any type whatsoever operating in the marine environment and includes hydrofoil boats, air-cushion vehicles, submersibles, and floating craft of any type.”</i>
SUA Convention ¹⁷⁴	Art. 1: <i>“... a vessel of any type whatsoever not permanently attached to the sea-bed, including dynamically supported craft, submersibles, or any other floating craft.”</i>
Anti-Fouling Convention ¹⁷⁵	Art. 2 (9): <i>“‘Ship’ means a vessel of any type whatsoever operating in the marine environment and includes hydrofoil boats, air-cushion vehicles, submersibles, floating craft, fixed or floating platforms, floating storage units (FSUs) and floating production storage and off-loading units (FPSOs).”</i>
Bunker damage Convention ¹⁷⁶	Art. 1 (1): <i>“‘Ship’ means any seagoing vessel and seaborne craft, of any type whatsoever.”</i>
BWM Convention ¹⁷⁷	Art. 1 (12): <i>“‘Ship’ means a vessel of any type whatsoever operating in the aquatic environment and includes submersibles, floating craft, floating platforms, FSUs and FPSOs.”</i>

49. What this overview has made clear is that the amount of definitions given does not allow for a uniform concept in general international law of the sea or maritime law. It is not possible to unequivocally consider MASSs as ships or not consider them as such. In many ways, this is understandable as the definitions given above are in the first place meant to ensure the application of the specific treaty they are contained within, leading to a broader or narrower definition depending on the subject matter. As such, the instruments on pollution contain very broad definitions, while for example the COLREGs-definition does not include submarines and contain the requirement of transportation.¹⁷⁸ Accordingly, when determining whether MASS fall within the definition of ship or vessel, a treaty-by-treaty basis will have to be followed¹⁷⁹

¹⁷² Amendments to the 1954 International Convention for Prevention of Pollution of the Sea by Oil, 11 April 1962, UNTC, vol. 600, 332.

¹⁷³ International Convention on Oil Pollution Preparedness, Response and Cooperation, 30 November 1990, UNTC vol. 1891, 51.

¹⁷⁴ Convention for the Suppression of Unlawful Acts against the Safety of Maritime Navigation, 10 March 1988, UNTC vol. 1678, 201.

¹⁷⁵ International Convention on the control of harmful anti-fouling systems on ships, 5 October 2001, IMO Doc. AFS/CONF/26 Annex.

¹⁷⁶ International Convention on Civil Liability for Bunker Oil Pollution Damage, 23 March 2001, IMO Doc. LEG/CONF.12/19

¹⁷⁷ International Convention for the control and management of ship's ballast water and sediments, 13 February 2004, IMO Doc. BWM/CONF/36.

¹⁷⁸ Brendan Gogarty & Meredith Hagger, 'The Laws of Man over Vehicles Unmanned: The Legal Response to Robotic Revolution on Sea, Land and Air', *Journal of Law, Information and Science*, 2008, vol. 19, no. 1, 114.

¹⁷⁹ Supra note 22, Michael N. Schmitt & David S. Goddard, 2016, 577.

6.4 What of other sources?

50. Before concluding whether the abovementioned definitions are sufficient in the present international law framework, it is worth taking note of some of the national laws applicable to the subject as well as some of the visions in legal doctrine. On that front, the Belgian Shipping Code¹⁸⁰ gives for definition of a ship:

*“elk tuig, met of zonder eigen beweegkracht, met of zonder waterverplaatsing, dat drijft of heeft gedreven en dat wordt gebruikt of geschikt is om te worden gebruikt als middel van verkeer te water, met inbegrip van luchtkussenvaartuigen doch met uitsluiting van vaste tuigen, watervliegtuigen en amfibievoertuigen.”*¹⁸¹

51. Similar definitions can be found in the legal systems of the US,¹⁸² the Netherlands,¹⁸³ Germany¹⁸⁴ and the United Kingdom.¹⁸⁵ While these definitions are not equal and some are applied stricter than others,¹⁸⁶ they share similar qualities and none exclude MASS from the scope of applicability of the term “ship” from the start. The same can be said of the definition given by the American Branch of the International Law Association which considers as vessel: *“any human-made device, including submersible vessels, capable of traversing the sea.”*¹⁸⁷ A similar definition is found in the International Maritime Dictionary which sees vessel as a *“general term for all craft capable of floating on water and larger than a rowboat. The term vessel includes every description of watercraft or other artificial contrivance used or capable of being used as a means of transportation on water.”*¹⁸⁸ Thus, from a national law perspective, MASS can be included into the definition of ship for the purposes of developing an international legal concept as no definition considers have a crew on board essential.¹⁸⁹

¹⁸⁰ Wet van 8 mei 2019 tot invoering van het Belgisch Scheepvaartwetboek, BS augustus 2019.

¹⁸¹ Own translation: “Every craft with or without own propulsion, with or without displacement, which floats or has floated and which is used or fit to be used as a way of transport across the water, including air-cushion vehicles, though excluding solid structures, water aircraft or amphibious craft”, see Art. 1.1.1.3, § 1, 1° Belgian Shipping Code.

¹⁸² 1 USC §3: “every description of water-craft or other artificial contrivance used or capable of being used as a means of transportation on the water.”; Note that in the US, the Supreme Court has in the past utilized a “reasonable observer” test to determine whether a certain construct qualified as a vessel or not, see *Lozman v. City of Riviera Beach* 133 S.Ct. 735, 2013, AMC 1, at 739.

¹⁸³ Art. 194, Book 8 on the registration of seagoing ships: “any man-made construct designed with a floating capability may, in principle, constitute a ship”; Seagoing ships themselves are defined in Art. 8:2 (1) BW as those ships that, “according to their construction, are intended exclusively or principally for floating on the sea.”

¹⁸⁴ “every vehicle of more than insignificant size, capable of floating and provided with a hollow, the purpose of which is to be moved on water” as found in Sarah Gahlen, ‘Ships Revisited: A Comparative Study’, *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2014, vol. 20, 25.

¹⁸⁵ Merchant Shipping Act of 1995, s. 313: “any description of a vessel used in navigation.”; see also supra note 61, Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 2019, 29.

¹⁸⁶ An example is the refusal of the Danish authorities to allow for the passage of a mobile offshore drilling unit through the Danish Straits as they did not consider the craft a “vessel” under the passage regime’s definition; see e.g. *Case Concerning Passage through the Great Belt (Finland v. Denmark)*, ICJ, 1991-1992.

¹⁸⁷ George K. Walker, *Definitions for the Law of the Sea: Terms not Defined by the 1982 Convention*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 2012, 55-61 & 300-301.

¹⁸⁸ René De Kerchove, *International Maritime Dictionary*, Van Nostrand, 1961 (2nd Ed.), 890.

¹⁸⁹ Damilola Osinuga, ‘Unmanned Ships: Coping in the Murky Waters of Traditional Maritime Law’, *Poredbeno Pomorsko Pravo*, 2020, vol. 174, 85.

52. Legal doctrine can roughly be divided into two camps. First, there are those who seek to define the term ship in a general way to determine whether a MASS can be considered a ship. Gahlen for example has tried to find a common ground among the many elements of what constitutes a vessel and has determined that a vessel must have the following characteristics: floatability; capacity for controlled movement on water; capacity for the carriage of goods and persons beyond its mass; and engagement in maritime navigation.¹⁹⁰ Bork has added a minimum size to this list.¹⁹¹ Daum from his end prefers to consider the quality of “transportation” as an essential characteristic and believes merely transporting sensors does not suffice to be considered a ship.¹⁹² In this however, he is contradicted by McLaughlin who believes no such requirement exists or should exist.¹⁹³

53. The second category chooses to see the LOSC’s lack of clarity as a blessing in disguise, allowing for a flexible definition of the term ‘ship’, also taking into account the many IMO-conventions.¹⁹⁴ In this camp, we find Noyes who believes we should learn to accept the fact that a uniform definition of ship does not exist and should not exist, as its classification will be distinct depending on the treaty in question.¹⁹⁵ He is supported in this by the opinions of Nandan and Rosenne¹⁹⁶ and Petrig.¹⁹⁷ Veal, Tsimplis and Serdy take this one step further and would allow the individual flag States themselves to determine what is a ship and what isn’t.¹⁹⁸ Immediately, this author is of the opinion that such a choice might induce chaotic effects and tensions into the international maritime domain. McKenzie finally attempts to find a middle ground between the more basic views of Noyes and the more chaotic ones of Veal, Tsimplis and Serdy by allowing significant freedom for the flag State, but narrowing which devices one may consider ship by link to the sea and relevant flag and coastal State duties. In this, he is followed by René-Jean Dupuy and Daniel D. Vignes.¹⁹⁹

¹⁹⁰ Sarah Fiona Gahlen, ‘Ships Revisited: A Comparative Study’, *The Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2014, vol. 20, no. 4, 252.

¹⁹¹ Katharina Bork et al., ‘The Legal Regulation of Floats and Gliders – In Quest of a New Regime?’, *Ocean Development & International Law*, vol. 39, no. 3, 298.

¹⁹² Oliver Daum, ‘The Implications of International Law on Unmanned Naval Craft’, *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 80-84.

¹⁹³ Robert Veal, ‘Regulation and Liability in Autonomous Shipping: A Panoptic View’, *Tulane Maritime Law Journal*, 2020, vol. 45, 112.

¹⁹⁴ Robert Veal & Michael Tsimplis, ‘The Integration of Unmanned Ships into the Lex Maritima’, *Lloyd’s Maritime and Commercial Law Quarterly*, 2017, vol. 2, 303.

¹⁹⁵ John E. Noyes, ‘Interpreting the 1982 Law of the Sea Convention and Defining Its Terms’ in George K. Walker (ed.), *Definitions for the Law of the Sea: Terms Not Defined by the 1982 Convention*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 2012, 55.

¹⁹⁶ Satya N. Nandan & Shabtai Rosenne, *United Nations convention on the Law of the Sea 1982: A Commentary*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 1985-2011, vol. 2, 46.

¹⁹⁷ Anna Petrig, ‘The Commission of Maritime Crimes with Unmanned Systems: An Interpretive Challenge for the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea’ in Malcolm D. Evans and Sofia Galani (eds.), *Maritime Security and the Law of the Sea: Help or Hindrance?*, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020, 126.

¹⁹⁸ Supra note 69, Simon McKenzie, 2020, 394.

¹⁹⁹ René-Jean Dupuy and Daniel Vignes, *A Handbook on the New Law of the Sea vol. 2*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 1991, 842.

7. Conclusion: the necessity of new international regulation?

54. This leaves the reader with one final question: is the current framework up for the job? Immediately, it should be stated that only one small aspect of the many legal challenges was discussed here, therefore necessitating that any conclusion is taken with a grain of salt. Having said so, at least until fully autonomous ships enter the maritime domain, the current framework can indeed cope. Throughout the world, MASSs are already sailing or under development.²⁰⁰ At this moment and under the LOSC, these vehicles should indeed be considered as ships or vessels, so as to benefit from both their rights and duties in the international maritime domain. This is also the view of Coito²⁰¹ and Allen²⁰² and McKenzie,²⁰³ even if it is not currently accepted by everyone.²⁰⁴

55. That is not to say new regulation is not advised into the future. Especially as fully autonomous ships start sailing the seas, many of the evolutionary interpretations that are possible today – considering operators shore-side as master and crew for example²⁰⁵ – will no longer be possible. Today however, for remote-controlled MASS, considering these as ships for the purposes of the law of the sea and maritime law is in line with the object and purpose of these treaties as well as with the technical evolutions that are currently ongoing as part of the 4th industrial revolution. It would be more dangerous and inductive to legal uncertainty to not consider MASSs as ships than to consider them as such.

²⁰⁰ Andrew H. Henderson, 'Murky Waters: The Legal Status of Unmanned Undersea Vehicles', *Naval Law Review*, 2006, vol. 53, 55.

²⁰¹ Joel Coito, 'Maritime autonomous Surface Ships: New Possibilities – And Challenges – In Ocean Law and Policy', *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2021, vol. 97, 299.

²⁰² *Supra* note 83, Craig H. Allen, 2018, 503.

²⁰³ Rui Li, 'On the Legal Status of Unmanned Ships', *China Oceans Law Review*, 2019, no. 4, 173.

²⁰⁴ Oliver Daum, 'The Implications of International Law on Unmanned Naval Craft', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1, 85.

²⁰⁵ Thanasis Karlis, 'Maritime Law issues related to the operation of unmanned autonomous cargo ships', *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 2018, vol. 17, 119.

Bibliography (chronologically, alphabetical if same date)

International Treaties

Convention VII relating to the Conversion of Merchant Ships into Warships, 18 October 1907.

Convention on the High Seas, 29 April 1958, 450 UNTS 11.

Amendments to the 1954 International Convention for Prevention of Pollution of the Sea by Oil, 11 April 1962, UNTC, vol. 600, 332.

United Nations Convention on Conditions for Registration of Ships, 7 February 1968 (not yet in force), UN Doc. TD/RS/CONF/19/Add.1.

Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 23 May 1969, UNTC vol. 1155, 331.

International Convention relating to intervention on the high seas in cases of oil pollution casualties, 29 November 1969, UNTC vol. 970, 211.

International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage, 29 November 1969, UNTC vol. 973, 3.

International Convention on the establishment of an international fund for compensation for oil pollution damage, 18 December 1971, UNTC vol. 1110, 57.

Convention on the international regulations for preventing collisions at sea, 20 October 1972, UNTC vol. 1050, 16.

Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter, 29 December 1972, UNTC vol. 1046, 138.

International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea, 1974, 1 November 1974, UNTC vol. 1184-1185, 2.

Athens Convention Relating to the Carriage of Passengers and their Luggage by Sea, 13 December 1974, UNTC vol. 1463, 20.

International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships, as amended by the 1978 Protocol, 17 February 1978, UNTC vol. 1340, 61.

United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, 10 December 1982 Montego Bay, UNTS vol. 1833, 3.

Convention for the Suppression of Unlawful Acts against the Safety of Maritime Navigation, 10 March 1988, UNTC vol. 1678, 201.

International Convention on Salvage, 28 April 1989, UNTC vol. 1953, 165.

International Convention on Oil Pollution Preparedness, Response and Cooperation, 30 November 1990, UNTC vol. 1891, 51.

International Convention on Liability and Compensation for Damage in Connection with the Carriage of Hazardous and Noxious Substances by Sea, 2 May 1996, not yet in force.

Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes or Other Matter, 7 November 1996.

International Convention on Civil Liability for Bunker Oil Pollution Damage, 23 March 2001, IMO Doc. LEG/CONF.12/19.

International Convention on the control of harmful anti-fouling systems on ships, 5 October 2001, IMO Doc. AFS/CONF/26 Annex.

International Convention for the control and management of ship's ballast water and sediments, 13 February 2004, IMO Doc. BWM/CONF/36.

Nairobi International Convention on the removal of wrecks, 18 May 2007, UNTC vol. no. not available, see <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=080000028053c3a0>.

National Laws

(United States of America) United States Code

(United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland) UK Merchant Shipping Act of 1995.

(Belgium) Wet van 8 mei 2019 tot invoering van het Belgisch Scheepvaartwetboek, BS augustus 2019.

UN/IMO Documents

UNCLOS III, Report of the Chairman of the Drafting Committee, UN Doc. A/CONF.62/L.40 (1980), OR XIII, 97

UN Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea, Navigation on the High Seas: Legislative History of Part VII, Section (Articles 87, 89, 90-94, 96-98) of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, at 80, UN Sales No. E.89.V2 (1989).

Amendments to the International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue (IAMSAR) Manual Annex 11, IMO Doc. MSC.1/Circ. 1415, 25 May 2012.

IMO MSC, *Final Reports: Analysis of Regulatory Barriers to the Use of Autonomous Ships*, IMO Doc. MSC 99/INF.3 of 18 January 2018.

IMO MSC, *Interim Guidelines for MASS Trials*, IMO MSC Circ 1604 of 14 June 2019.

United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), *Review of Maritime Transport 2019*, UNCTAD/RMT/2019, 83.

IMO MSC, *Outcome of Regulatory Scoping Exercise for the Use of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships*, IMO MSC Circ 1638 of 3 June 2021.

Legal Committee of the International Maritime Organization, 108th Session, LEG 108, 26-30 July 2021.

International Jurisprudence

Legal Consequences for States of the Continued Presence of South Africa in Namibia (South West Africa) Notwithstanding Security Council Resolution 276 (1970), ICJ Advisory Opinion, 21 June 1971.

Aegean Sea Continental Shelf (Greece v. Turkey), ICJ Judgement, 19 December 1978.

Passage through the Great Belt (Finland v. Denmark), ICJ, 1991-1992, discontinued.

Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary v. Slovakia), ICJ Judgement, 25 September 1997.

Dispute regarding Navigational and Related Rights (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), ICJ Judgement, 13 July 2009.

Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), ICJ Judgement, 20 April 2010.

National Jurisprudence

Lozman v. City of Riviera Beach, Supreme Court of the United States, 2013, 133, 735.

Legal doctrine

Books (also includes non-legal books)

I. G. Gidel, *Le Droit International Public De La Mer*, 1934..

Isaac Asimov, *I, Robot*, Gnome Press, New York, 1950.

René De Kerchove, *International Maritime Dictionary*, Van Nostrand, 1961 (2nd Ed.).

René-Jean Dupuy and Daniel Vignes, *A Handbook on the New Law of the Sea vol. 2*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 1991.

Donald R. Rothwell and Sam Bateman, *Navigational Rights and Freedoms and the New Law of the Sea*, Martinus Nijhoff, The Hague/London, 2000.

David Freestone, Richard Barnes, and David Ong (eds.) *The Law of the Sea, Progress and Prospects*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2006.

Peter A. Dutton (ed.), *Military Activities in the EEZ: A U.S.-China dialogue on Security and International Law in the Maritime commons*, Naval War College/China Maritime Studies Institute No. 7, 2010.

Satya N. Nandan & Shabtai Rosenne, *United Nations convention on the Law of the Sea 1982: A Commentary vol. 2*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 1985-2011.

Alexander Gillespie, *A History of the Laws of War Vol. 3*, 2011, Hart Publishing, Oxford | Portland.

Natalie Klein, *Maritime Security and the Law of the Sea*, Oxford University Press, 2011.

John E. Noyes, 'Interpreting the 1982 Law of the Sea Convention and Defining Its Terms' in George K. Walker (ed.), *Definitions for the Law of the Sea: Terms Not Defined by the 1982 Convention*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 2012.

George K. Walker, *Definitions for the Law of the Sea: Terms not Defined by the 1982 Convention*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Leiden | Boston, 2012.

Myron Nordquist, John Moore & Ronan Long (eds.), *Legal Order in the World's Oceans*, Brill Nijhoff, 2017.

Malcolm D. Evans and Sofia Galani (eds.), *Maritime Security and the Law of the Sea: Help or Hindrance?*, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020.

Journal Articles

Stephanie Showalter, 'The Legal Status of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles', *Marine Technology & Society Journal*, 2004, vol. 38, no. 1.

Richard Shaw, 'What is a Ship in Maritime Law?', *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2005, vol. 11.

Andrew H. Henderson, 'Murky Waters: The Legal Status of Unmanned Undersea Vehicles', *Naval Law Review*, 2006, vol. 53.

Katharina Bork et al., 'The Legal Regulation of Floats and Gliders – In Quest of a New Regime?', *Ocean Development & International Law*, 2008, vol. 39, no. 3.

Brendan Gogarty & Meredith Hagger, 'The Laws of Man over Vehicles Unmanned: The Legal Response to Robotic Revolution on Sea, Land and Air', *Journal of Law, Information and Science*, 2008, vol. 19.

Rob McLaughlin, 'Unmanned Naval Vehicles at Sea: USVs, UUVs and the Adequacy of the Law', *Journal of Law, Information and Science*, 2011, vol. 21.

Markus Wagner, 'Taking Humans Out of the Loop: Implications for International Humanitarian Law', *Journal of Law Information and Science*, 2011, vol. 21, no. 2.

Jing Geng, 'The Legality of Foreign Military Activities in the Exclusive Economic Zone and under UNCLOS', *Merkourios* 2012, vol. 28, Issue 74.

Arthur B. Evans, 'Jules Verne's Dream Machines: Technology and Transcendence', *Extrapolation*, 2013, vol. 54, no. 2.

Sarah Gahlen, 'Ships Revisited: A Comparative Study', *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2014, vol. 20.

Eric Van Hooydonck, 'The Law of Unmanned Merchant Shipping – an Exploration', *Journal of International Maritime Law*, 2014, vol. 20.

J. Ashley Roach, 'Today's Customary International Law of the Sea', *Ocean Development and International Law*, 2014, vol. 45, no. 3.

Paul W. Pritchett, 'Ghost Ships: Why the Law Should Embrace Unmanned Vessel Technology', *Tulane Maritime Law Journal*, 2015, vol. 40, no. 1.

Michal Chwedczuk, 'Analysis of the Legal Status of Unmanned Commercial Vessels in the U.S. Admiralty and Maritime Law', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2016, vol. 47, no. 2.

Gotthard Mark Gauci, 'Is it a Vessel, a Ship of a Boat, is it Just a Craft, or is it Merely a Contrivance', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2016, vol. 47.

Michael N. Schmitt & David S. Goddard, 'International Law and the military use of unmanned maritime systems', *International Review of the Red Cross*, 2016, vol. 98, no. 2.

Douglas Guilfoyle, 'Maritime Law Enforcement Operations and Intelligence in an Age of Maritime Security', *International Law Studies*, 2017, vol. 93.

Robert Veal & Michael Tsimplis, 'The Integration of Unmanned Ships into the Lex Maritima', *Lloyd's Maritime and Commercial Law Quarterly*, 2017, vol. 2.

Craig H. Allen, 'Determining the Legal Status of Unmanned Maritime Vehicles: Formalism vs Functionalism', *Journal of Maritime and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 4.

Matt Bartlett, 'Game of Drones: Unmanned Maritime Vehicles and the Law of the Sea', *Auckland University Law Review*, 2018, vol. 24.

Jeremy A. Carp, 'Autonomous Vehicles: Problems and Principles for future Regulation', *University of Pennsylvania Journal of Law and Public Affairs*, 2018, vol. 4.

Aldo Chircop, 'Testing International Legal Regimes: The Advent of Automated Commercial Vessels', *German Yearbook of International Law*, 2018, vol. 60, no. 1.

Oliver Daum, 'The Implications of International Law on Unmanned Naval Craft', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1.

Elrich D. Grome, 'Spectres of the Sea: The United States Navy's Autonomous Ghost Fleet, Its Capabilities and Impacts, and the Legal Ethical Issues That Surround', *Journal of Maritime Law and Commerce*, 2018, vol. 49, no. 1.

Thanasis Karlis, 'Maritime Law issues related to the operation of unmanned autonomous cargo ships', *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 2018, vol. 17.

Aristotelis Komianos, 'The Autonomous Shipping Era. Operational, Regulatory, and Quality Challenges', *The International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 2018, vol. 12, no. 2.

Robert Veal, Michael Tsimplis & Andrew Serdy, 'The Legal Status and Operation of Unmanned Maritime Vehicles', *Ocean Development and Coastal Law*, 2018, vol. 50.

Daniel F. Carlson, Alexander Fürsterling, e.a., 'An affordable and portable autonomous surface vehicle with obstacle avoidance for coastal ocean monitoring', *Hardware X*, April 2019, vol. 5, article e00059.

Natalie Klein, 'Maritime Autonomous Vehicles within the International Law Framework to Enhance Maritime Security', *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2019, vol. 95.

Rui Li, 'On the Legal Status of Unmanned Ships', *China Oceans Law Review*, 2019, no. 4.

Henrik Ringbom, 'Regulating Autonomous Ships – Concepts, Challenges and Precedents', *Ocean Development and International Law*, 2019, vol. 50, no. 2-3.

Amit Sharma, Tae-eun Kim & Salman Nazir, 'Catching up with time? Examining the STCW competence framework for autonomous shipping', *Ergoship 2019 Conference Paper*.

Glenn Wright, 'Intelligent Autonomous Ship Navigation Using Multi-sensor Modalities', *International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 2019, vol. 13.

Paul David, 'From Automation to Autonomy – Can the Law Keep up?', *Australian and New Zealand Maritime Law Journal*, 2020, vol. 34, no. 1.

Andrzej Felski & Karolina Zwolak, 'the Ocean-Going Autonomous Ship: Challenges and threats', *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 2020, vol. 8.

Samantha Jordan, 'Captain, My Captain: A Look at Autonomous Ships and How They Should Operate under Admiralty Law', *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review*, 2020, vol. 30, no. 2.

Simon McKenzie, 'When is a Ship a Ship? Use by State Armed Forces of Uncrewed Maritime Vehicles and the United Nations Convention on the Law the Sea', *Melbourne Journal of International Law*, 2020, vol. 21, no. 2.

Hitoshi Nasu & David Letts, 'The Legal Characterization of Lethal Autonomous Maritime Systems: Warship, Torpedo, or Naval Mine?', *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2020, vol. 96.

Damilola Osinuga, 'Unmanned Ships: Coping in the Murky Waters of Traditional Maritime Law', *Poredbeno Pomorsko Pravo*, 2020, vol. 174.

Robert Veal, 'Regulation and Liability in Autonomous Shipping: A Panoptic View', *Tulane Maritime Law Journal*, 2020, vol. 45.

Joel Coito, 'Maritime autonomous Surface Ships: New Possibilities – And Challenges – In Ocean Law and Policy', *International Law Studies Series – US Naval War College*, 2021, vol. 97.

Jennifer Parker, 'The Challenges Posed by the Advent of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships for International Maritime Law', *Australian and New Zealand Maritime Law Journal*, 2021, vol. 35, nr. 1.

Kai Tong & Tong Xiao, 'International Symposium on the Law of the Sea – Development Challenges and Prospects', *China Oceans Law Review*, 2021, vol. 17, no. 3.

News Articles

See Erik Sofge, 'Robot Boats Hunt High-Tech Pirates on the High-Speed Seas', *Popular Mechanics*, 2 October 2009, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/navy-ships/a2234/4229443/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

Isaac Arnsdorf, 'Rolls-Royce Drone Ships Challenge \$375 Billion Industry: Freight', *Bloomberg Business*, 25 February 2014, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2014-02-25/rolls-royce-drone-ships-challenge-375-billion-industry-freight>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Evan Ackerman, 'Unmanned Cargo Ships Face Industry Resistance, Are a Good Idea Anyway', *IEEE Spectrum*, 27 February 2014, <https://spectrum.ieee.org/unmanned-cargo-ships-face-industry-resistance-are-a-good-idea-anyway>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

X, 'Ghost Ships', *The Economist*, 8 March 2014, <https://www.economist.com/technology-quarterly/2014/03/06/ghost-ships>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

N. R. P., 'Top 10 Most Powerful Weapons of The Israeli Military', *Defencyclopedia*, 30 January 2015, <https://defencyclopedia.com/2015/01/30/top-10-most-powerful-weapons-of-the-israeli-military/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

Inmarsat Partners with Rolls Royce on Autonomous Ship Project, *Inmarsat*, 8 September 2015, <https://www.inmarsat.com/en/news/latest-news/maritime/2015/inmarsat-partners-with-rolls-royce-on-autonomous-ship-project.html>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

Danielle Sullivan Kaminski, 'Who's to Blame When no one is Manning the Ship?', *Law360*, 6 October 2016, <https://www.law360.com/articles/847478>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

Kyle Mizokami, 'Pentagon Confirms Russia Has a Submarine Nuke Delivery Drone', *Popular Mechanics*, 8 December 2016, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/weapons/a24216/pentagon-confirm-russia-submarine-nuke/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Sam LaGrone, 'Updated: Chinese Seize U.S. Navy Unmanned Vehicle', *USNI News*, 16 December 2016, <https://news.usni.org/2016/12/16/breaking-chinese-seize-u-s-navy-unmanned-vehicle>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

X, 'Unmanned Vehicles Could Aid Search and Rescue', *The Maritime Executive*, 16 December 2016, <https://www.maritime-executive.com/editorials/unmanned-vehicles-could-aid-search-and-rescue>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

Jane Perlez & Matthew Rosenberg, 'China Agrees to Return Seized Drone, Ending Standoff, Pentagon Says', *The New York Times*, 17 December 2016, <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/12/17/world/asia/china-us-drone.html>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Missy Ryan & Dan Lamothe, 'Pentagon: Chinese Naval Ship Seized an Unmanned U.S. Underwater Vehicle in South China Sea', *Washington Post*, 17 December 2016, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/checkpoint/wp/2016/12/16/defense-official-chinese-naval-ship-seized-an-unmanned-u-s-ocean-glider/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

Kris Osborn, 'The Navy's Future Swarm Ghost Fleet', Real Clear Defense, 1 February 2017, www.realcleardefense.com/2017/02/02/the_navy039s_future_swarm_quotghost_fleet_quot_290008.html, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

George Dvorsky, 'Robots Are Already Replacing Human Workers at an Alarming Rate', *Gizmodo*, 28 March 2017, <https://gizmodo.com/robots-are-already-replacing-human-workers-at-an-almarmi-1793718198>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

Anna Versai, 'Artificial Intelligence and Moore's Law', *Technowize*, 14 May 2017, <https://www.technowize.com/artificial-intelligence-moores-law/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Max Greenwood, '7 sailors missing in ship collision found dead', *The Hill*, 27 June 2017, <https://thehill.com/policy/defense/338307-seven-sailors-missing-in-ship-collision-found-dead/>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

The Editorial Team, 'Allianz: Human error behind 75 percent of marine casualties', *Safety4Sea*, 25 August 2017, <https://safety4sea.com/allianz-human-error-behind-75-percent-of-marine-casualties/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

John Churchill, 'When the Screens Went Black', *Maersk Post*, 14 September 2017, <https://careers-origin.maersk.com/home/stories/when-the-screens-went-black>, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

The Editorial Team, 'Global supply and demand for seafarers', *Safety4Sea*, 5 February 2018, <https://safety4sea.com/global-supply-demand-seafarers-2/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Christian Wienberg, 'Maersk's CEO Can't Imagine Self-Sailing Box Ships in His Lifetime', *Bloomberg Technology*, 15 February 2018, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018->

02-15/maersk-ceo-can-t-imagine-self-sailing-box-ships-in-his-lifetime, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

X, 'Nautilus urges IMO to take heed of human factors in 'smart ship' review', *Nautilus International*, 9 May 2018, <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/news/nautilus-urges-imo-to-take-heed-of-human-factors-in-smart-ship-review/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

Kimberly Tam & Kevin Jones, 'Cyber-Risk Assessment for Autonomous Ships', *Cyber Security*, Conference Paper, May 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325195302_Cyber-Risk_Assessment_for_Autonomous_Ships.

Andrew Russ, 'The human element – the effects of fatigue on ship safety', *Safety4Sea*, 3 July 2018, <https://safety4sea.com/the-human-element-the-effects-of-fatigue-on-ship-safety/>, last consulted 14 May 2022.

X, 'Rolls-Royce and Finferries demonstrate world's first Fully Autonomous Ferry', *Rolls Royce*, 3 December 2018, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/2018/03-12-2018-rr-and-finferries-demonstrate-worlds-first-fully-autonomous-ferry.aspx>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Sam LaGrone, 'Navy Wants 10-Ship Unmanned "Ghost Fleet" to supplement Manned Force', *USNI News*, 13 March 2019, <https://news.usni.org/2019/03/13/navy-wants-ten-ship-3b-unmanned-experimental-ghost-fleet>, last consulted 13 May 2022.

X, 'Detecting Fish From Ocean-Going Robots To Complement Ship-Based Surveys', *NOAA Fisheries News*, 22 August 2019, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/feature-story/detecting-fish-ocean-going-robots-complement-ship-based-surveys>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

Stefan Seltz-Axmacher, 'How One Change to Shipping Goods Could Change the Way We Live', *World Economic Forum*, 6 September 2019, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/09/from-sail-to-self-driving-what-the-history-of-shipping-tells-us-about-the-future-of-autonomous-electric-freight/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

X, 'NYK Conducts World's First Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships Trial', *NYK News Release*, 30 September 2019, https://www.nyk.com/english/news/2019/20190930_01.html, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

M. Wingrove, 'Autonomy Tested for Oil Spill Removal', *Riviera Maritime Media*, 7 January 2020, <https://www.rivieramm.com/news-content-hub/news-content-hub/autonomy-tested-for-oil-spill-removal-57354>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

The Maritime Executive, 'Hyundai Plans First Ocean-Going Autonomous Ship voyage by Years' End', *The Maritime Executive*, 27 July 2021, <https://www.maritime->

executive.com/article/hyundai-plans-first-ocean-going-autonomous-ship-voyage-by-year-s-end, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Jack Richard Dougherty, 'Autonomous Vessels are Becoming a Commercial Reality', *The Maritime Executive*, 24 September 2021, <https://www.maritime-executive.com/editorials/autonomous-vessels-are-becoming-a-commercial-reality>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Raunek Kantharia, 'Can Futuristic Unmanned Cargo Ships Sail Without Seafarers', *Marine Insight*, 11 January 2022, <https://www.marineinsight.com/future-shipping/rolls-royces-futuristic-unmanned-ships-will-sail-without-seafarers/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

Websites

International Chamber of Shipping, 'Explaining Shipping', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/explaining/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

International Chamber of Shipping, 'Shipping and world trade: driving prosperity', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-driving-prosperity/>, last consulted on 11 May 2022.

International Chamber of Shipping, <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-driving-prosperity/>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

International Chamber of Shipping, 'Shipping and World Trade: Global Supply and Demand for Seafarers', <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-global-supply-and-demand-for-seafarers/> last consulted on 12 May 2022.

IMO, *IMO takes first steps to address autonomous ships*, <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/PressBriefings/Pages/08-MSC-99-MASS-scoping.aspx>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

X, 'Nine-dash line', *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nine-dash_line, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

X, 'Protector USV', *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Protector_USV, last consulted on 13 May 2022.

X, 'Sea Hunter', *Wikipedia*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sea_Hunter, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

X, 'AUTONOMOUS SHIP PROJECT, KEY FACTS ABOUT YARA BIRKELAND', *Kongsberg*, <https://www.kongsberg.com/maritime/support/themes/autonomous-ship-project-key-facts-about-yara-birkeland/>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

X, 'German Explosive Remote-Control speedboats of WW1 and WW2', *Standing Well Back, IED & EOD Evolutions*, <https://www.standingwellback.com/german-explosive-remote-control-speedboats-of-ww1-and-ww2/>, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

Other sources

United States Patent Office, 'Letter of Patent no. 613809 – Method of and Apparatus for Controlling Mechanism of Moving Vehicle of Vehicles', Nicholas Tesla, 8 November 1898.

Tommy T. B. Koh, *A Constitution of the Oceans*, 6 and 11 December 1982, Montego Bay, http://www.un.org/Depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/koh_english.pdf, last consulted on 15 May 2022.

Alexander M. G. Walan, 'Anti-Submarine Warfare (ASW) Continuous Trail Unmanned Vessel (ACTUV)', *Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency*, 2010, <https://www.darpa.mil/program/anti-submarine-warfare-continuous-trail-unmanned-vessel>, last consulted on 14 May 2022.

Sven Gerhard, *Safety and Shipping 1912-2012 From the Titanic to Costa Concordia: An Insurer's Perspective from Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty*, Allianz, 2012.

DoD, Defense Science Board, Summer Study on autonomy, 2016, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/AD1017790>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Jouni Saarni, Sini Nordberg-Davis & Hannu Makkonen, 'From Innovation to Markets-Redefining Shipping', *Remote and Autonomous Ships – The Next Stage*, Rolls-Royce, 2016.

European Commission, *Autonomous Shipping Initiative for European Waters*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815012>, last consulted on 12 May 2022.

Ronald O'Rourke, 'Navy Large Unmanned Surface and Undersea Vehicles: Background and Issues for Congress', Congressional Research Service, 11 May 2022, summary.